

**FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF SOCIAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN
WITH DISABILITIES**

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Abstract: The article reveals the content of the reforms carried out in recent years in our country for the social protection of children with disabilities. The definitions given by international organizations operating in the field of social protection of children with disabilities in relation to the concept of "social protection", as well as the study of this concept in sociology and social work, are scientifically-theoretically analyzed. Scientific views of sociologist scientists of our country on social protection of children with disabilities are revealed. Appropriate scientific proposals and recommendations were made through a sociological analysis of advanced foreign experiences in the social protection of children with disabilities.

Keywords: Sociology, Social Protection, Social service, Social Work, Child with disabilities, Child needs, Child rights, Social assistance.

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In the world, the number of persons with disabilities is growing in proportion to the demographic growth of the population, as well as as a result of the growing number of infectious and chronic diseases. According to the World Health Organization, more than 15% of the world's population is made up of persons with disabilities, and more than 100 million of them are children[1]. Due to the rapid growth in the number of persons with disabilities, the burden on them by the state in the field of coverage and protection of Social Services is also increasing. This necessitates the implementation and improvement of systemic reforms in the allocation of social protection and socio-material assistance to children with disabilities in our country. The ratification of the convention on the rights of persons with disabilities[2] served to improve national legislation in order to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of children with disabilities and to improve the system of social protection.

The concept of "social protection" is a special object of research in the socio-humanitarian Sciences, Scientific Research is being carried out. Each science considers certain components of social protection as necessary for society as a social phenomenon, based on the subject areas of science, lawyers believe that guarantees of human rights, economists are part of state social policy, sociologists are an important social institution in the context of the development of society, employees of social work are practical activities that contribute to the direct But at the same

time, there is also a mutual contradiction, controversy in the definition and approaches to the concept of “social protection” by the scientific community. Recently, scientists have been promoting the use of a simplified approach to describing the concept of "social protection". An example of a simplified approach in this context is the following definition: “social protection is a system of satisfying the material, spiritual and other needs of a person”[3]. Considering the definition of the concept of “Social protection”, this concept was first used in the US Social Protection Act in 1935. In this legal document, cases of disability, old age, unemployment, premature death are legalized as a compulsory insurance system. Later, this concept was developed in the UN system of generally recognized international norms of social protection, and these international legal acts serve as a theoretical basis for conducting research on social protection. According to the International Labor Organization's approach, “social protection is a measure taken by the state and society against economic, social crises resulting from a halt or significant reduction in income due to illness, production accidents, as well as unemployment, old age, birth, death, socio - medical care, subsidies to families with children”[4]. We can also see a slight expansion by the World Health Organization, the International Association for Social Security, in the processes of adoption of conventions and recommendations on social insurance and social assistance, minimum income for workers in case of incapacity for work, labor protection and wage guarantees.

The International Labor Organization describes the social protection of children with disabilities as follows: “social protection of persons with disabilities is a system that meets their needs, taking into account the risks, social inequalities and obstacles faced by children with disabilities during various activities”[5].

The UNICEF International Children's fund interprets social protection as follows: “social protection is a set of public policies and programs aimed at preventing or protecting poverty, vulnerability, social crisis throughout the life cycle among groups of the population in need of social protection” [6]. It is important to support and care for children with disabilities at all stages of their entire life cycle. The inclusive social protection system should consist of a system of measures aimed at overcoming discrimination, stigma, stereotypes, environmental and attitude barriers towards children with disabilities. It is important to cover the benefits and social services that allow children with disabilities to fully exercise their rights and join society, which will be necessary throughout their lives, as well as to apply benefits.

Doctor of sociology, professor M.Bekmurodov his scientific activities, attached particular importance to the academic development of social work in the training of Higher Education personnel in the field of social protection. According to the

Uzbek scientist, "social work is a very multifaceted activity that covers all spheres of society and human life. However, the experience of training highly qualified personnel in this regard shows that the academic development of social work in our country is successfully progressing in the field of social protection of children"[7]. Therefore, the social protection system of children with disabilities should be further expanded to provide professional personnel and improve the quality of social services provided to them.

Professor M.Ganieva believes that in the integration of children with disabilities into society, special attention is paid to solving their everyday problems, solving issues of improving infrastructure, overcoming existing obstacles, and various problems, in turn, will serve to improve the mechanisms of their sociocultural adaptation[8]. Hence, the social protection of children with disabilities plays an important role in their meaningful cultural recreation, the creation of the necessary conditions, the use of a systematic and complex approach in social protection.

Professor Sh. Sadigova The main directions of state policy aimed at strengthening the social protection of the population, especially children, in our country emphasized, first of all, the further improvement of existing regulatory legal acts. In particular, the impact of material and spiritual assistance to disabled people, children without breadwinners, citizens without care, single elderly people, low-income families, increasing the effectiveness, further strengthening the activity and responsibility of state and non-governmental organizations, self-government bodies such as the neighborhood, and the wide involvement of entrepreneurs and representatives of private business in the noble cause were scientifically substantiated[9]. Therefore, in the social protection of children with disabilities, the classification of subjects of Social Protection, their functional and organizational-structural analysis, plays an important role.

Doctor of sociology, professor N.Latipova studied the issues of social protection of family and children, including "social protection is the sum of social actions aimed at the formation of an integrated and sustainable society through the development of complex institutional mechanisms that create certain conditions for ensuring justice and security, eliminating social risks, overcoming their consequences"[10] he described. Hence, the essence of social protection of children with disabilities is of a broad nature, special attention should be paid to the provision of benefits and benefits to them, the allocation of subsidies from the state in satisfying their needs, and the provision of professional social services.

We can mention that the concept of "social protection" is considered from the point of view of several interdisciplinary studies:

- in sociology, they consider social protection as a system for ensuring a decent life and free development of a person;
- in demography, social protection is seen as a system that helps to maintain the demographic situation, ensure the well-being and health of the nation;
- Social Work employees view different categories of the population as practical activities that directly facilitate the provision of social services;
- in economic science, social protection is studied from the point of view of the right to provide the population with material resources, to prevent poverty, as well as to support a person in difficult situations for reasons that do not depend on unemployment, disability or oneself.

An important role in meeting the needs of children with disabilities necessary for life, improving the quality of living standards and reducing the risk of poverty is played by their social support and protection. In the experience of developed countries, the principle of social protection based on law is put forward, we can see that children with disabilities have equal rights and opportunities in life, like other children, a social protection system is proposed based on an inclusive social protection approach that promotes their integration into society and public participation.

Below we will get acquainted with the experience of working with children with disabilities in the social protection system of developed countries.

Method of working with children with disabilities. The child is 10 years old. She lives at home with her parents and sister. His father officially works. The Father receives a monthly salary in the amount of the average salary. They live on rent. The child has intellectual, physical and emotional disabilities. She needs help to eat, dress and walk.

The needs of the child: services, adapted technical devices, personal assistant.

Let's see what work is being done with this state of the child in France[11].

A) if a child needs special devices, it can be said that the costs incurred for this service will be covered by other insurance companies as another option by the Social Security departments, with an amount of 65% until they are listed. Social Security, but this possibility;

b) personal assistance. If the child's parents want to hire a personal assistant and keep someone busy, they will have to pay for it. However, discounts can be given when paying taxes for them;

c) services and other types of social assistance. The child's parents can use the benefits provided for children with disabilities to pay expenses that are not financed by Social Security Departments. The child can also use special education and care services, depending on their needs. These services are carried out free of

charge. The child's family can receive discounts of up to 50 percent when paying income tax;

G) income protection. If the child's parents stopped working to take care of their child, he will have the right to receive an additional fee of at least the 4th category;

D) expenses related to disability. If the disability costs exceed 289 euros per month, additional compensation can be obtained in addition to the childhood disability benefit. Also, the child's parents can receive additional compensation for disability-related expenses every 10 years. These can be expenses that have gone for the additional adaptation of the family vehicle or the adaptation of the House;

e) housing. The child can receive a residential pension due to the fact that he lives on rent. Also, the landlord can take advantage of a 25% tax deduction every 5 years if the amount of expenses that the House has adapted to the needs of a disabled person exceeds the specified amount.

We will consider this situation of the child on the example of the experience of social protection of children with disabilities in Great Britain[12].

Needs and services of the child.

a) services, devices and social assistance. If there is a need to adapt the house to the needs of the child, grants designed for children with disabilities can be used to cover family expenses. Jobs that require financing include the costs of expanding doors, installing risers for climbing the second floor, adapting toilets, bathrooms. To cover these costs, different amounts are allocated geographically;

b) personal assistance (care service). Payments are provided in local budgets based on the assessment of the needs for the support of the child's caregiver;

C) income protection. Non-working parents have the right to child care benefits or preferential loans. Parents also have the right to receive deductions from taxes.

G) expenses related to disability. The child has the right to receive a disability pension due to the fact that he is not 16 years old and has difficulty walking, needs more care in relation to a healthy child. The amount of the allowance depends on the level of assistance required for it and is determined by the social worker;

d) housing. The child's parents have the right to receive rental money due to the fact that they live on a rental basis.

Having studied advanced foreign experience in the social protection of children with disabilities, we came to the following conclusions.

- in international scientific research and foreign experiments, there are conflicting opinions in determining the concept of "social protection", and in scientific publications and literature, social protection is expressed mainly as a

concept in the content of providing material assistance to population groups in need of social support.

- in advanced foreign experiments, the principle of social protection based on law is put forward, providing inclusion in the social protection system, which provides equal rights and opportunities in life for children with disabilities, their integration into society and public participation, like other children.

- in foreign experience, the system of social protection of children with disabilities includes a mechanism for distinguishing the amount of benefits and benefits provided for them, ultimately supporting people with disabilities, depending on the consequences of disability and the degree of illness. at all stages of the life cycle.

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